

**MUASSASALARNING NOMLANISHIDA DAVLAT TILINING O‘RNI
THE ROLE OF THE STATE LANGUAGE IN THE NAME OF
INSTITUTIONS**

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Annotatsiya : Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasining davlat tili hisoblangan o‘zbek tilining davlat korxonalarida hamda turli xildagi muassasalarning nomlanishidagi ahamiyati, o‘zbek tilining mavqeyi bayon qilinadi. Muassasalarning nomlanishida davlat tilining ahamiyati va o‘tini haqida aytib o‘tilgan hamda o‘zbek tilining tarixi va bugungi kundagi rivojlanish jarayonlari aks ettirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Muassasa, davlat tili, korxonalar, tashkilot, jarayon, rivojlanish, til oilalari, qonun, moddalar, ona tili, dunyo tillari.

Annotation: In this article, the importance of the Uzbek language, which is considered the state of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the naming of various types of information and the status of the Uzbek language is made. The importance and roots of the state language are mentioned in the naming of the institutions, and the history and current processes of the Uzbek language are reflected.

Key words: Institution, state language, organization, organization, process, project, language families, law, Unga language, world languages.

KIRISH

O‘zbekistonning “Davlat tili to‘g‘risida”gi qonuni bundan 33 yil avval, 1989-yil 21-oktabrda – mustaqilligimiz e‘lon qilinganiga qariyb ikki yil qolganida qabul qilingan. Mamlakatimizda hali ham avtoritar tuzum jazo o‘tayotgan o‘ta og‘ir sharoitda xalqimiz taqdiri va kelajagini hal qiladigan bu qonunni qabul qilish oson bo‘lmadi.

Darhaqiqat, o‘sha davrda o‘zbek tili davlat tili sifatida xalqimizni birlashtirgan, jamiyatimizni buyuk maqsadlar sari safarbar etuvchi qudratli kuch sifatida maydonga chiqdi. Ayni paytda bu O‘zbekiston mustaqilligi sari qo‘yilgan ilk dadil qadam edi. 1989-yilda qabul qilingan “Davlat tili to‘g‘risida”gi qonunda o‘z aksini topgan muhim huquqiy normalar keyinchalik 1992-yilda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi

Konstitutsiyasi – Mustaqillik kengashining 4-moddasida quyidagicha mustahkamlanganligini ham ta’kidlash lozim:

“O‘zbek tili O‘zbekiston Respublikasining davlat tilidir. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi o‘z hududida yashovchi barcha millat va elatlarning tillari, urf-odatlar va an’analari hurmat qilinishini ta’minlaydi, ularning rivojlanishi uchun sharoit yaratadi”[1].

INTRODUCTION

The Law of Uzbekistan "On the State Language" was adopted 33 years ago, on October 21, 1989 - about two years before the declaration of our independence. It was not easy to pass this law, which will decide the fate and future of our people, in the extremely difficult conditions where the authoritarian regime is still serving its sentence in our country.

Indeed, at that time, the Uzbek language as the state language emerged as a powerful force that united our people and mobilized our society towards great goals. At the same time, it was the first bold step towards the independence of Uzbekistan. It should also be noted that the important legal provisions reflected in the Law "On State Language" in 1989 were later strengthened in 1992 in Article 4 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan - Independence Council as follows:

"Uzbek is the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Republic of Uzbekistan ensures that the languages, customs and traditions of all nations and peoples living in its territory are respected, and creates conditions for their development." [1]

MATERIALLAR VA USULLAR

Yangi O‘zbekistonni barpo etish yo‘lidagi ezgu intilishlarimiz, harakatlarimiz hal qiluvchi bosqichga ko‘tarilmoqda. Shu tariqa milliy o‘zligimiz va g‘ururimiz timsoli bo‘lgan ona tilimiz beqiyos kuch va ilhom manbai bo‘lib xizmat qilmoqda.

Bu haqda gapirganda, Prezidentimizning 2020-yil 20-oktabrda imzolangan “Mamlakatimizda o‘zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish va til siyosatini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi farmoni alohida e’tiborga loyiq ekanini alohida ta’kidlash joiz. Mazkur hujjatda o‘zbek tilini xalqimiz ijtimoiy hayotida va xalqaro miqyosda tubdan oshirish, yoshlarimizni vatanparvarlik, milliy an’ana va qadriyatlarimizga sadoqat ruhida tarbiyalash, davlat tilini to‘liq joriy etish belgilangan. mamlakatimizda. chavandozlar bilan bog‘liq istiqboldagi vazifalar ko‘zda tutilgan. Prezident farmonida til siyosatini rivojlantirishning strategik maqsadlari va ustuvor yo‘nalishlari, O‘zbekistondagi millat va elatlarning tillarini

asrab-avaylash va rivojlantirish, o‘zbek tilini davlat tili sifatida o‘rganish uchun shart-sharoit yaratish, til siyosatini rivojlantirish belgilab berildi. belgilangan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our noble aspirations and actions aimed at building a new Uzbekistan are reaching a decisive stage. In this way, our mother tongue, which is a symbol of our national identity and pride, serves as an incomparable source of strength and inspiration.

When talking about this, it should be noted that the President's decree "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language in our country and improve the language policy" signed on October 20, 2020 deserves special attention. In this document, the Uzbek language is to be radically increased in the social life of our people and at the international level, to educate our young people in the spirit of patriotism, loyalty to national traditions and values, and to fully introduce the state language in our country. future tasks related to riding are envisaged. In the Presidential Decree, the strategic goals and priority directions of language policy development, preservation and development of the languages of the nations and peoples of Uzbekistan, creation of conditions for learning the Uzbek language as the state language, and development of the language policy were defined.

TADQIQOT VA MUHOKAMA

Aytish joizki, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasida o‘zbek tilining maqomi huquqiy jihatdan mustahkamlangan. “O‘zbek tili to‘g‘risida”gi qonun qabul qilingandan so‘ng barcha davlat hujjatlari o‘zbek tilida yuritila boshlandi, gazeta va jurnallar o‘zbek tilida chop etila boshlandi. 1993-yil 2-sentabrda “Lotin tiliga asoslangan o‘zbek alifbosini tashkil etish to‘g‘risida”gi qonun qabul qilinganidan so‘ng mamlakatimiz har tomonlama rivojlanib, jahon kommunikatsiya tizimidan munosib o‘rin egallashiga keng yo‘l ochdi. Shu o‘rinda statistik ma‘lumotlarga e‘tibor qaratsak, dunyoda 5600 dan ortiq til mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan faqat 200 tasi davlat tili sifatida qabul qilingan. Ular orasida o‘zbek tilining ham borligi uning naqadar sof, mukammal, sof va jozibali ekanligining yorqin dalilidir. Rus tilshunosi, professor A. M. Kozlyanina “O‘zbek tili musiqa ohangi kabi nafis va jozibali” deb bejiz aytmagan.

Biroq, bu o‘rinda savol tug‘ilishi tabiiy: o‘zbek tili biror joyga nom berishga yaramaydimi?! Afsuski, barchamizga ma‘lumki, ko‘chalardagi do‘konlar, supermarketlar, turli ustaxonalar, go‘zallik salonlari, osmono‘par binolar, bog‘chalar nomlari o‘zbek tilida emas, balki boshqa xorijiy tillarda yozilganiga guvoh bo‘lishimiz mumkin. Bu haqiqatni isbotlash uchun katta ilmiy izlanishlar qilish shart

emas, qo‘lingizga ruchka, qalam olib ko‘chaga chiqish kifoya. Qanchalik achinarli bo‘lsa-da, biz bunga ko‘nikib ketyapmiz! Axir biz O‘zbekistonda yashaymiz, nega joylarni o‘zbekcha nomlay olmaymiz? Bunga kim aybdor: davlat hokimiyati yoki o‘zbek millati? Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda O‘zbekistonda osmono‘par binolar qurilayotganiga qaramay, ularning nomlari hamon ingliz tilida ekani haqida turli fikrlar bildirilayotganiga duch kelishimiz mumkin. Masalan, ulardan biri Toshkent markazida qurilgan “Nest one” deb nomlangan turar-joy binosining nomi o‘zbekcha emas, inglizcha ekanligini aytadi! Vaholanki, bu imorat O‘zbekistonda o‘zbeklar tomonidan qurilgan (inglizlar emas!) Bu so‘zlarni ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan birida yozilgan maqolada ham uchratishimiz mumkin: “Demak, quruvchi o‘zbekmi, uning dastxati yaqqol ko‘rinib turishi kerak. qurgan bino, bu esa quruvchining o‘zligini yo‘qotmaganidan dalolatdir inobatga olsak, ular tilshunoslarni jalb qilgan taqdirda ham, o‘zbek tilining boyligini xalqqa ko‘rsatish, yangi so‘z va iboralarning o‘zbekcha talqinini joriy etishda yetakchilik qilishi kerak”.

AQSH, Buyuk Britaniya, Germaniya, Rossiya, Xitoy, Hindiston, Turkiya va boshqa mamlakatlarning 60 ga yaqin universitetlari va 100 dan ortiq maktablarida o‘zbek tili o‘qitilayotgan bir paytda biz binolarimizni inglizcha yoki ingliz tilida nomlashimizni qanday tushunishimiz kerak. ruscha?! Shu o‘rinda BMT vakillarining til haqida aytgan faktini eslaylik: “Bir paytlar odamlar so‘zlashadigan tillar soni 7-8 mingga yetgan bo‘lsa, bugungi kunda sayyoramizda 6000 ta til mavjud va ularning 90 foizi. Bular asosan tsivilizatsiya tufayli o‘z madaniyatini yo‘qotayotgan oz sonli xalqlarning tillaridir, boshqalari esa, masalan, 80% Afrika tillarida so‘zlashuvchi aholi hali ham o‘z yozuviga ega emas, tilshunoslarning fikriga ko‘ra, yana 25 yil o‘tgach, bugungi kunda qo‘llaniladigan o‘n tildan biri saqlanib qoladi.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi hududidagi davlat organlari, tashkilot va muassasalarda davlat tiliga oid qonun hujjatlarining ayrim normalari buzilganiga guvoh bo‘lishimiz mumkin. “Davlat tili to‘g‘risida”gi qonunning 10-moddasiga ko‘ra, korxonalar, muassasalar, tashkilot va jamoat birlashmalarida ish yuritish davlat tilida olib borilishi mumkin, lekin ko‘pchilik xodimlari o‘zbek tilini bilmaydigan jamoalarda ish yuritilishi mumkin. boshqa tillarda, shuningdek davlat tilida amalga oshiriladi. Biroq ayrim davlat tashkilotlari, organlari va muassasalarida ish yuritish davlat tilida emas, balki boshqa tillarda, jumladan, rus tilida olib borilmoqda. Bu o‘z navbatida davlat tiliga hurmat va e‘tiborning pasayishiga sabab bo‘layotgani barchamizga ayon. Shuning uchun ham O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Ma‘muriy

javobgarlik to'g'risidagi kodeksining 42-moddasiga Adliya vazirligi tomonidan "Davlat tili to'g'risidagi qonun hujjatlarini buzish" deb nom berilgan bo'lsa-da, bu moddada belgilangan talablarga rioya qilmaslik bilan bog'liq munosabatlar qamrab olinmagan. davlat organlari va tashkilotlarida ishlarni olib borishda davlat tili haqidagi qonun hujjatlarining. . Bu holat ayrim davlat organlarida davlat tili to'g'risidagi qonun hujjatlariga rioya etilmasligi, ish yuritishning davlat tilida olib borilmayotganiga olib kelmoqda, deb ta'kidladi Adliya vazirligi. 2020-yil 25-aprelda Adliya vazirligining Ukraina Jinoyat kodeksining 42-moddasiga quyidagi mazmundagi qo'shimcha kiritish taklifi bilan: "Davlat organlarida ishlarni olib borishda davlat tili haqidagi qonun hujjatlari talablariga rioya qilmaslik va tashkilotlar mansabdor shaxslarga asosiy hisob-kitob miqdorining ikki baravaridan besh baravarigacha miqdorda jarima solishga sabab bo'ladi" degan 2020-yil 25-apreldagi ommaviy axborot vositalarida maqola shaklida e'lon qilinganiga qaramay, hech qanday o'zgartirish kiritilmaganini ko'rishimiz mumkin. hali. Fuqarolik kodeksining 42-moddasiga o'zgartirish kiritish: "Davlat organlari va tashkilotlarida ishlarni olib borishda davlat tili to'g'risidagi qonun hujjatlari talablariga rioya etmaslik mansabdor shaxslarga asosiy hisob-kitob miqdorining ikki baravaridan besh baravarigacha miqdorda jarima solishga sabab bo'ladi. "

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

It should be noted that the status of the Uzbek language has been legally strengthened in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. After the adoption of the law on the Uzbek language, all state documents began to be kept in Uzbek, newspapers and magazines were published in Uzbek. On September 2, 1993, after the adoption of the law "On the establishment of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin language", our country developed in all respects and paved the way for it to occupy a worthy place in the world communication system. Let's pay attention to statistics here: there are more than 5600 languages in the world, and only 200 of them are accepted as state languages. The presence of the Uzbek language among them is a clear proof of how pure, perfect, pure and attractive it is. Professor A. M. Kozlyanina, a Russian linguist, did not for nothing say that "the Uzbek language is as elegant and attractive as the melody of music."

However, it is natural to ask a question here: is the Uzbek language not suitable for naming a place?! Unfortunately, as we all know, we can witness that the names of shops, supermarkets, various workshops, beauty salons, skyscrapers, and kindergartens on the streets are not written in Uzbek, but in other foreign languages.

To prove this fact, you don't need to do a huge scientific research, it's enough to go out into the street with a pen and a pen in your hand. Despite how sad it is, we are getting used to it! After all, we live in Uzbekistan, why can't we name places in Uzbek? Who is to blame for this: state authorities or the Uzbek nation? In social networks, we may come across different opinions expressed that despite the fact that skyscrapers are being built in Uzbekistan, their names are still in English. For example, one of them says that the name of the residential building called "Nest one" built in the center of Tashkent is not in Uzbek, but in English! However, this building was built in Uzbekistan by the Uzbeks (not the British!) We can also find these words in an article written on one of the social networks: "So, whether the builder is Uzbek, his signature should be clearly visible on the building he built, and this indicates that the builder has not lost his identity. The signature appears first in names. Frankly speaking, the neglect of the Uzbek language in the official press is quite high. More precisely, state institutions are leading in this regard. In fact, even if they involve linguists, they should take the lead in showing the richness of the Uzbek language to the people, introducing the Uzbek interpretation of new words and phrases."

At a time when the Uzbek language is taught in about 60 universities and more than 100 schools of the USA, Great Britain, Germany, Russia, China, India, Turkey and other countries, how should we understand that we name our buildings in English or Russian?! Just here, let's recall the fact given by the representatives of the UN about language: "Once upon a time, the number of languages spoken by people reached 7,000 to 8,000, but today there are 6,000 languages on our planet, and 90 percent of them are on the verge of extinction. These are mainly the languages of a small number of nations that are losing their culture due to civilization. Some of the people who speak these languages have writing, while others do not. For example, 80% of the African language-speaking population still does not have its own writing. According to linguists, after another 25 years, one out of ten languages that are in use today will be preserved.

We can witness the violation of some norms of legislation on the state language in state bodies, organizations and institutions in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to Article 10 of the Law "On the State Language", business in enterprises, institutions, organizations and public associations can be carried out in the state language, but in communities where the majority of employees do not know the Uzbek language, it can be carried out in other languages as well as the state language. However, in some state organizations, bodies and institutions, proceedings

are conducted not in the state language, but in other languages, including Russian. It is clear to all of us that this, in turn, causes a decrease in respect and attention to the state language. That is why, although Article 42 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan was named "Violation of the legislation on the state language" by the Ministry of Justice, this article did not cover relations related to non-compliance with the requirements of the legislation on the state language in the conduct of work in state bodies and organizations. . According to the Ministry of Justice, this situation leads to the non-compliance with the legislation on the state language in some state bodies and to the fact that proceedings are not carried out in the state language. On April 25, 2020, the proposal of the Ministry of Justice to add the following to Article 42 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine: "Failure to comply with the requirements of the legislation on the state language in the conduct of work in state bodies and organizations will result in officials being fined from two to five times the amount of the basic calculation" in the media on April 25, 2020 we can see that despite the fact that it was published in the form of an article, no changes have been made yet. Amending Article 42 of the Civil Code: "Failure to comply with the requirements of the legislation on the state language in the conduct of work in state bodies and organizations shall result in officials being fined from two to five times the amount of the base calculation."

XULOSA

Xulosa o'rnida aytish mumkinki, ona tili millatning ruhi, borlig'imiz va birligimiz, davlat timsoli ekanligini inobatga olib, uni asrab-avaylash va rivojlantirish har bir fuqaroning insoniy burchidir. Binobarin, oldimizda o'zbek tilini yanada rivojlantirish, uning davlat tili sifatidagi mavqei va nufuzini yanada mustahkamlash borasida ulkan va mas'uliyatli vazifalar turibdi.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, taking into account that the mother tongue is the soul of the nation, our existence and unity, the symbol of the state, it is the human duty of every citizen to preserve and develop it. Therefore, we have great and responsible tasks ahead of us in terms of further development of the Uzbek language, further strengthening of its position and prestige as the state language.

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